

APPRAISAL OF RADIO JOURNALISTS' PERCEPTION AND PROMOTION OF GOOD GOVERNANCE IN DELTA STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The paper titled, Appraisal of Radio Journalists' Perception and Promotion of Good Governance in Delta State, Nigeria assessed the perception of radio journalists on good governance and how they use their radio station to promote it. Social Responsibility serves the theoretical foothold. This study employs the pragmatic approach of research design, which informs the choice of survey and interview methods. Using homogenous snowball and purposive sampling techniques, a total of 40 radio journalists and fifteen radio stations domiciled in the State were studied. Findings revealed that many of the journalists do not understand what good governance truly means and the various ways the radio can be used to promote it. It also revealed that most of journalists think the average Nigerians already know what good governance is and entails. The study concludes that since the radio is a powerful political tool especially at the grass roots, the ignorance of radio journalists of the power of the radio in the education and mobilization of the populace for active participation in politics and to make political leaders accountable to the people has huge implication for democracy and media practice in the nation. Thus, to perform their societal responsibility well, radio journalists should have ample knowledge of what good governance truly means because you cannot give what you do not have.

Keywords: Radio, journalists, perception, promotion and good governance

Introduction

Good governance is crucial for the development of any human society. It is about the participation of citizen in government and the delivery of key goods and services by governments. Good governance ensures that all diverse machineries of government carry out their specific functions and responsibilities. It is pertinent to note that the government is not the only principal actors in good governance. The other three main actors are the military, civil societies and the masses. Thus, governance is not the exclusive reserve of a government, individuals that belong to any of the other three groups of key players may play a role in decision-making or in influencing the decision-making process.

There are different types of government including, democracy, socialism, communism, monarchy, oligarchy and autocracy etc. With a majority of the world's nations accepting the legitimacy of democracy, it is widely acclaimed as one of the best forms of government (Obasi et al, 2025). This could be because democracy, the government of the people, for the people and by the people seems to be one of the most civilized forms of governance, although not in all cases.

For instance, Nigeria, a country that operates democracy is one of the most mis-governed nations in the world. Her ranking as the third-worst country globally by the Chandler Institute of Governance (CIG) and 158th on the United Nations' Human Poverty Index 36th among other similar rankings give credence to this fact (Obasi & Obasi, 2022; Aondover, 2019). Thus, depending on the kind of government in charge or the caliber of the leaders at the helm of affairs, governance can be either good or bad.

For governance to be seen as good, it must have certain feature. The World Bank Group established some variables called, "World Governance Indicators" for measuring or assessing governance globally. These indicators include -voice and accountability; political stability and absence of violence/terrorism; government effectiveness, regulatory quality; rule of law and lastly, control of corruption (World Bank, 2022).

Similarly, UNESCAP (2009) gives the eight parameters for measuring the performance or non-performance of any governance as, participation (i.e. equal access of every citizen of that nation to the systems of their government), rule of law (i.e. impartial legal systems that respect human rights of every citizen of that nation), transparency (i.e. openness, knowledge and access of the masses to means and process of decision making), responsiveness (i.e. presence of functional, strong and responsible social institutions), consensus-oriented (i.e. national agenda that mediates, unifies the needs, perspectives, and expectations of all sections of the citizenry), equity and inclusiveness (i.e. ensuring that every member of the nation including the poor, marginalized get equal, same treatment), effectiveness and efficiency (i.e. judicious and sustainable use of natural and human resources for common good), accountability (i.e. being financially open and responsible to the people).

A closer look at the above two categories of indicators that characterize good governance globally show that active participation of members of a nation and accountability financially and otherwise of political leaders are the underlying features. This view corresponds with those of Okocha et al., (2023) who give the typical features of good governance especially in Africa as, existence of minimum level of democracy, checks and balances (horizontal accountability), participation and elections (vertical accountability), and respect for basic human rights (which include political rights), and the ability to meet the needs of society as well as efficiently utilises public resources to meet those needs.

It follows that absence of any of the above feature from a government means bad governance. It equally shows that bad governance is the major obstacle to socio-economic development. This view finds bearing with that of Komodromos (2020) who discloses that governance significantly influences development. Unfortunately, due to the lack of control by the public over governance through elections and other crucial administrative decision-making process, most African nations including Nigeria are plagued with various aftermath of bad government including poverty, insecurity, the high of unemployment, high mortality rate and much more.

This is where mass media come in. Various studies (Komodromos, 2020; Obasi & Aondover, 2023; Okocha et al., 2023) show that very few institutions affect human beings as much as the mass media do. As the principle means of communication in the contemporary society, most people look on the media for information to navigate through life on daily basis and for succor as well as to keep in check all those whose actions and inactions directly or indirectly affect the lives of others in the society.

Due to the strong political and other influence of the mass media in human lives, various terms have been used to describe the media including, fourth estate of the realm, societal watchdog, societal mirror, oxygen of democracy among others (Obasi & Aondover, 2023; Okocha et al., 2023). Hence, in various types of government especially in a democracy where freedom of expression and independence of the press occupy an enviable position, the mass media plays significant and diverse roles in promoting good governance.

The argument is that there can be no good governance if those governed do not know what their leaders are doing or not doing or contemplating to do (Singh, 2015). Thus, the primary duty of the press is to provide its citizens with necessary information and to educate them on the activities of the government. In the intricate tapestry of a democratic society, political awareness serves as the thread that weaves together the fabric of informed citizenship.

A populace well-versed in political matters is not merely citizens but is an essential component of a thriving democracy (Sabo & Kente, 2024). This awareness, often shaped by information dissemination and public engagement, is the compass guiding individuals as they navigate the turbulent waters of political decision-making (McQuail cited in Obasi & Aondover, 2023).

In the realm of information dissemination, radio's role in creating political awareness has transcended generations and technological advancements, solidifying its status as an indispensable and dynamic medium especially in Africa (Komodromos, 2020; Iheanacho et al., 2021). The ability of radio to stand out as an effective means of mass communication especially in Africa is because it is pervasive, flexible, available, local, cheap, extensive, personal, oral, portable, speedy and efficient.

Several studies (Fraser, 2016; Gagliardone, 2016; Komodromos, 2020) indicate that most Africa countries who are doing well politically including Zambia, Kenya, Ghana have robust radio systems they use to boost active participation of the masses in political activities. The interactive nature of the media not only helps to promote political accountability but also gives a platform for the voiceless and powerless members of the society to express themselves (Fraser, 2016). It was against this background that this paper sets out to examine the extent radio promote good governance in Delta State.

Research questions

1. To what extent do radio journalists in Delta State understand the concept of good governance?
2. What are the perceptions of radio journalists' perception on publics' level of awareness of good governance?
3. To what extent do radio stations in Delta State promote good governance in Nigeria?
4. What are the challenges that radio journalists in Delta State face in the promotion of good governance?

Radio, as Africa's Preferred Medium of Communication

Radio is a portable audio device that passes messages, information to a heterogeneous audience using electromagnetic waves. Although various terms have been used to describe the radio including, "magic box", "Africa's medium" "blind medium" (Owens-Ibie & Obasi, 2023) and much more, the term, "Africa's medium", stands out. Africa's medium means that radio is a very common means of mass communication among Africans and their most effective medium of information dissemination (Owens-Ibie & Obasi, 2023; Ajisafe, 2021; Apuke, 2017; Nkwam-Uwaoma et al., 2021).

For instance, Uchegbuo and Azubuike (2023) attribute the popularity of radio in Africa to the fact that it eliminates linguistic diversity, and gives the uneducated the opportunity and platform to participate in democratic processes. Thus, as an audio medium, radio does not exclude those in the society who cannot read or write (Ajisafe, 2021; Owens-Ibie & Obasi, 2023). This could be the reason why over 75% of households in Africa have access to the radio and why there are more than 800 million radios in Sub-Saharan Africa (Komodromos, 2020).

Another feature that makes radio common in Africa is because it is portable, handy and can be carried with ease. This makes it possible for people even those in rural areas to listen to radio anywhere and anytime. Moreover, when compared to television, radio is also cheap to acquire and maintain even in rural areas where living conditions are relatively poor (Apuke, 2014 cited in Owens-Ibie & Obasi, 2023).

Moreover, as a medium of mass communication, radio is very powerful in rural communication for the fact that it requires no special technical skills to operate and can be easily operated even with finger battery in areas where there is no electricity. This simplicity makes it possible for radio to easily transcend literacy and language barriers and therefore easy to engage remote and marginalized communities (Mawokomayi & Osunkunle, 2019). Radio is equally very flexible and convenient to use. Hence, anyone including farmers can listen to it even while performing other responsibilities.

Furthermore, radio signal is very invasive and can be accessed even in remotest part of the world. Its accessibility is one of the underlying reasons for radio's effectiveness in political communication

especially among rural and marginalized populations that may lack access to other mass media forms in Africa.

Again, radio programme is relatively cheaper to produce and distribute. Unlike television or internet access, which can incur significant costs, radio contents are mostly free and widely available (Ajisafe, 2021; Owens-Ibie & Obasi, 2023). Thus, these unique characteristics especially, accessibility, simplicity, affordability, portability and the ability to reach diverse audiences sets radio apart as a political communication tool especially in Africa (Mawokomayi & Osunkunle, 2019; Sabo & Kente, 2024).

Factors that stifle professionalism in media coverage of governance in Nigeria

In discharging their duties, media professionals face lots of pressures that can affect their independence in treating information. Studies (Singh, 2015; Obasi, 2023; Okocha et al, 2023) identified some of the threats to press freedom as, undue ownership control of communication, regulations, commercial.

Concerning how ownership determine what goes into the media in Nigeria, Obasi (2023) disclose that one of the peculiar features of the media in Nigeria is the fact that greater percentage of mass media are either owned by government or private businessmen, who in most cases are friends to those in the government.

Thus, most media organizations are seen and treated as an extension of civil service with the resultant effect that bureaucracy not only becomes the order of the day but such media organizations end up being the mouthpiece of the government. Even when such media organizations are owed by private businessmen, the quest to make profit and to be in the good book of the government equally deter them from being balanced, extensive and fair in their communication.

Thus, the popular saying which states that a house dog knows the owners, the friends of its owner and even the friend to the friends of the owner becomes the case. Even though the media is supposed to be watch dog of the society, in reality the owners of most media organizations have primary interests they seek to protect and power that be that must be pleased at all cost to the detriment of safeguarding media professionalism.

Speaking on how the quest for commercial affects professionalism, Singh (2015) observes that the popular saying that, "he who plays the piper dictates the tune" explains it better. This means that the media industry is a business and like all businesses they are there to make profit. Unfortunately, this profit usually comes from external sources including advertisement, donation and much more.

Hence, it happens that in some cases, financial sponsors may influence either what is broadcasted or how and when it is broadcasted. No wonder, Obasi (2023) observe that journalists in Africa have a notorious reputation of "selling out" to proprietary, advertising and political controls. This practice of commercialization of media products and services beclouds their sense of judgment and professionalism.

Another factor that affects media professionalism is regulation, either from government or the media themselves. Studies reveal that right from the colonial era, there were many government regulations (Okechukwu, 2022; Owens-Ibie & Obasi, 2023; Nzeaka, 2023; Obasi et al, 2025) that could stifle media professionalism including the National Broadcasting Commission Act 1999, the Nigerian Press Council Act 60 of 2004, 2011 FOI Act, Protection from Internet Falsehood and Manipulation Bill of 2019, Hate Speech Bill of 2019 and lot more. For instance, Section 2(1)(b) and (c) of the NBC Act indicates that the NBC has no direct power to approve broadcasting licenses but the presidency.

Cases abound of Nigerians who were denied broadcast license because they had no political affiliations with the government (Okechukwu, 2022; Obasi et al, 2025). In the end, some of such intending owners may result to bribery and corruption and other unethical means in course of acquiring broadcast license.

This view reechoes with one of the basic assumptions of the Authoritarian theory of the press which states that the mass media does not exist in vacuum but take the form and colouration of its container like

liquid (Siebert et al., cited in Owens-Ibie & Obasi, 2023). It follows that the media are also influenced by the legal, social and political structures within which they operate.

Lack of training and retraining process: Another challenge is dearth of qualified personnel due to absence of regular training and retraining process of media professionals. Most of those in the media practice lack expert training lack technical knowledge of current practices in media world. Other factors that affect media professionalism include fund, lack of assurance cover for journalists, poor and delayed salaries to journalists, corruption in the media, harassment of journalists, lack of and inadequate access to public records (Singh, 2015).

Theoretical Frame work

The Social Responsibility Media Theory was propounded by F. S. Siebert, T. B. Paterson and W. Schramm in 1956. The theory argues that the press is duty-bound to be responsive and accountable to the society. A responsible press is one that provides a full, truthful, comprehensive and intelligent account of the day's events in a context which gives them meaning (Singh, 2015).

In outlining assumptions from Social Responsibility theory, Obagwu and Idris (2019) argue that media practitioners are required to be professional by reporting truthful, balanced, and complete reports of significant social events to assist the public in getting informed without encumbrances from extraneous factors. They equally observe that media and its practitioners have a sacred obligation to the society of exposing activities that could undermine governance practices by providing honest and accurate reports of activities of the government.

The principles and assumptions of this theory make it relevant to this article. Since this study investigated the extent radio stations in Delta State promote good governance, Social Responsibility theory came to bear as it underscored the importance of the masses having free access to information and the means to speak out and express their views.

This is because good governance requires the existence of checks and balances or accountability of the government which the media aptly provides. Accountability of the government will be possible only when the masses have adequate information and knowledge of activities of the government. Since knowledge is power, such knowledge gives people security and power to participate in governance and to navigate the society. Thus, the exchange of this information via the radio becomes the basis for an enlightened and politically active populace.

Methodology

The study employed the survey research and interview method to delve into the perceptions of radio journalists within Delta State, aiming to explore the contributions of radio stations in governance. To effectively gather insights into the influence of radio stations on governance in the region, a structured questionnaire and mediated interview were used as data collection instruments.

Population of the Study

Delta State has about 15 radio stations (Owens-Ibie & Obasi, 2023). These radio stations were studied including 98.7 FM (Bridge Radio, Asaba), 89.9 FM (Crown FM, Effuru), 100.9 FM (Trend FM, Asaba), 96.5 FM (Hot FM, Asaba), 97.9 FM (Voice of Delta Radio, Asaba), 93.1 (Quest FM, Patani), 89.9 FM (Melody FM, Warri), 88.6 FM (Joko FM, Ughelli), 97.9 FM (JFM, Jeremi), 106.7 (Riz FM, Warri), 100 FM (Kpoolo FM, Pidgin Broadcast, Warri), 101.9 FM (Sleek FM), 106.7 FM (Rize FM, Warri) and 103.7 FM (Delta State University (Delsu FM), Abraka).

Sample Size

A total of 40 radio journalists and fifteen radio stations domiciled in the State were studied.

Sampling Techniques

The study employed homogenous snowball and purposive sampling techniques. Using the homogenous and snowball sampling techniques, radio stations and radio journalists that were registered with Nigeria Union of Journalists (NUJ) in Delta State were chosen for questionnaire and interview session.

Questionnaire

47 (100%) copies of the questionnaire were administered to radio journalists, from which thirty (30) copies were correctly filled and collected in the month of March. This represents 63.8% feedback rate of the administered questionnaire. Details and analysis of the instrument are provided in the next sub-section.

Interview

The study also made use of mediated in-depth interview with an interview schedule to guide the dialogue. A total of 10 radio journalists were interviewed.

Findings and Discussion:

Demographic data of respondents:

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Source: Field Survey, 2024

RQ 1: The extent radio professionals in Delta State understand the concept of “good governance”

Table 1: The extent radio journalists in Delta State understand the concept of good governance

S/N		SA	A	D	SD	Mean
1.	Poor governance is responsible for high level of insecurity and violent conflicts in Nigeria	30	0	0	0	4
2.	Poor governance is responsible for high level of corruption in Nigeria	11	19	0	0	3.37
3.	Poor governance is responsible for high level of political misbehaviour in Nigeria	6	17	7	0	2.97
4	Poor governance is responsible for high level of poverty in Nigeria	11	8	11	0	3
5	Poor governance is responsible for weak social institutions in Nigeria	6	3	17	4	2.37
6	Poor governance is responsible for gross indiscipline in Nigeria	7	11	5	7	2.6

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Data in table 1 show mean value of 4 indicating unanimous consensus of the respondents that poor governance is responsible for high level of insecurity and violent conflicts in Nigeria. Results in the table further reveal mean value of 3.37 which is very above 2.5. This shows a stronger consensus and support by the respondents that poor governance is responsible for high level of corruption in Nigeria.

It equally shows mean value of 2.97 which is above 2.5, indicating positive tendency of the respondents to agree that poor governance is responsible for high level of political misbehaviour in Nigeria. Data in the same table also indicate mean value exactly at 3, indicating a tendency of the respondents to agree that there is link between poor governance and high level of poverty in the country.

Results in the data equally show mean value of 2.37 which is slightly below 2.5, indicating a high tendency of the respondents to disagree that poor governance is responsible for weak social institutions in Nigeria. In other words, most of the respondents do not see the high rate of corruption and other vices that has weakened most of the social institutions in Nigeria as an offshoot of poor governance in the nation. Lastly, figures in the table also reveal that mean value of 2.6 which is slightly above 2.5, indicating a weak positive tendency respondent to agree that poor governance is responsible for gross indiscipline in Nigeria.

Evidences from the interview session indicate that most of the definitions of good governance given by many of the respondents were incomplete and lacking in many regards. For instance, respondent 1

described good governance as: “Leadership human rights and accountability”. Similarly, respondent 2 described it as: “Accountability manage resource, have peace, security, discipline, corruption fee and violence and maintain of human”.

In the same vein, respondent 3 saw it as: “Governing from a human right perspective, can also be managing of resources, and public institutions”. But Komodromos (2020) defines governance as participation of citizen in government and the delivery of key goods and services by governments. In other words, good governance is a process whereby government officials conduct public affairs and manage public resources with utmost transparency and accountability for the common good of the populace.

Thus, from all indication, one may say that most of the radio journalists in Delta do not really understand what good governance truly means. No wonder, findings in table 1 indicate that about 7 (23.7%) of the radio journalists disagreed that poor governance is responsible for high level of political misbehaviour in Nigeria; 11 (36.7%) of them saw no link between poor governance and high level of poverty in the country and about 21 (70%) of them also failed to see corruption and other vices that has weakened most of the social institutions in Nigeria as an offshoot of poor governance in the nation and about 12 (40%) of them think that poor governance is not responsible for gross indiscipline in nation.

Going by the fact that all (100%) of the under studied radio journalists are over 30 years as shown by data in Figure 2, one may say that none of them is too young to claim to be uninformed or ignorant of the huge adverse effects of poor governance in the nation. But to perform their societal responsibility of watching and guarding the society well, radio journalists have to be well informed of what good governance truly means, if not they would not be able to perform their social functions properly.

RQ2: Radio journalists’ perception of publics’ level of awareness of good governance

Table 2: Radio Journalists’ perception of the publics’ level of awareness of good governance in Nigeria

S/N		SA	A	D	SD	Mean
1.	The average Nigerian has low understanding of what good governance is all about	13	13	4	0	3.3
2.	The average Nigerian has low understanding of the democratic values	3	21	6	0	2.9
3.	The average Nigerian is ignorant of the benefits of anti-corruption policy formulation and implementation	5	19	6	0	2.9
4	The average Nigerian is ignorant of specific actions to take against corrupt practices among government officials	0	10	20	0	2.33

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Figures in table 2 indicate mean value of 3.3 which is highly above is 2.5, indicating a strong positive tendency of the respondents to agree that the average Nigerian has low understanding of what good governance is all about. In other words, about 4 (13.3 %) of the respondents think the average Nigerian has high knowledge of what good governance truly means.

The data also reveal mean value of 2.9 which is above is 2.5, indicating a positive tendency of the respondents to agree that the average Nigerian has low understanding of the democratic values. In essence, about 6 (20%) of the respondents think the average Nigerian has adequate knowledge of what the democratic values are.

Results in the table also show mean value of 2.9 which is above is 2.5, indicating a positive tendency of the respondents to agree that the average Nigerian is ignorant of the benefits of anti-corruption

policy formulation and implementation. This implies that about 6 (20%) of the respondents think a typical Nigerian has understand what anti-corruption policy formulation and implementation is all about and it benefits to the society.

Lastly, data in the table also show mean value of 2.33, slightly below 2.5, indicating a weak negative tendency of the respondents to disagree that average Nigerian is ignorant of specific actions to take against corrupt practices among government officials. This means that 20 (90%) of the respondents feel a typical Nigerian knows specific actions to take to hold corrupt government officials accountable.

Literatures reveal that Nigeria is one of the most mis-governed nations in the world (Mtega, 2018; Okocha et al., 2023). If all Nigerians have high knowledge of what good governance and democratic values truly means and benefits of formulating and implementing anti-corruption policy as well as the right actions to take to hold corrupt government officials accountable, then Nigeria would not have been ranked the third-worst country in the world.

Since knowledge is power, the Social Responsibility theory makes it clear that a responsible press regularly provided complete, truthful, comprehensive and intelligent account of the daily activities of the government in a context which gives them meaning (Singh, 2015). The fact that radio stations and other media in the advanced world including CNN, Aljazeera etc still embark run political education programme indicate no nations can claim that its citizens have all the knowledge on their government and its process of governance. Thus, the above perception of some radio journalists of citizens' level of awareness of good governance in Nigeria is false and misleading.

RQ 3: The extent radio stations promote good governance in Nigeria

Table 3: Radio and good governance in Nigeria

S/N		SA	A	D	SD	Mean
1.	The radio can be used to boost citizens' participation in politics	3	24	3	0	3
2.	The radio can be used to make political leaders accountable to the people	6	17	7	0	2.97
3.	The radio can be used to strengthen democratic structures and social institutions	5	16	6	3	2.77
4	The radio can be used to mobilise public opinions for anti-corruption policy formulation and implementation	5	16	5	2	2.86

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Results in table 3 reveal mean value of 3 which is above 2.5, indicating a positive tendency of the respondents to agree that the radio can be used to boost citizens' participation in politics. This implies that 3 (10%) of the respondents do not know that as a means of mass communication, radio can be used educate and mobilise the populace for active participation in politics.

Data in the table also indicate mean value of 2.97 which is close to 3, indicating a positive tendency of the respondents to agree radio can be used to make political leaders accountable to the people. In other words, over 7 (23%) of the respondents are ignorant that radio can be a power weapon in the hands of the citizens to make political leaders accountable to them.

Figures in the table equally show mean value of 2.77 which is slightly above 2.5, indicating a weak positive tendency of the respondents to agree that the radio can be used to strengthen democratic structures

and social institutions. This means that about 9 (30%) of the respondents do not know the role of radio as a mass medium in nation building.

Lastly, figures in the table also indicate mean value of 2.86 which is slightly higher mean value 2.5, a weak positive tendency of the respondents to agree that radio can be used to mobilise public opinions for anti-corruption policy formulation and implementation. In other words, about 7 (23%) of the respondents do not know that the radio can be to mobilise public opinions for anti-corruption policy formulation and implementation.

Literatures indicate that the radio like other mass media can be used as a political tool especially at the grass roots (Sabo & Kente, 2024). The fact that some of the radio journalists are ignorant of the power of the radio in the education and mobilization of the populace for active participation in politics and to make political leaders more accountable to the people as well as the unique role of the radio as a mass medium in nation building has huge implication for media practice in the nation.

The Social Responsibility theory makes it clear that as the fourth estate of the realm, societal watch dog and oxygen of democracy the radio like other channels of mass media has unique role in nation building. To do so effectively, the media has to effectively inform, and educate the masses on the activities of the government. It is such knowledge that gives the masses power to participate in governance.

Table 4: The extent radio stations in Delta State is used in promoting good governance in Nigeria

S/N		Yes	No	Not Sure
1.	My radio station regularly launches educational campaigns on good governance in Nigeria	100% (30)	0% (0)	0% (0)
2.	My radio station has programmes that enthrone the formation of democratic values and good governance in Nigeria	100% (30)	0% (0)	0% (0)
3.	My radio station has programmes that tackle the government on the need to make and implement anti-corruption policies	86.7% (26)	13.3% (4)	0% (0)
4	My radio station has programmes that boost citizens' participation in politics	90% (27)	0% (0)	10% (3)
5	My radio station has programmes that mobilise citizens to demand for anti-corruption policy formulation and implementation in Nigeria	90% (27)	10% (3)	0% (0)
6	My radio station has programmes that teach the citizens other specific actions to take against corrupt practices among government officials	63.6% (19)	36.4% (11)	0% (0)

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Data in table 4 indicate over 100% of the respondents claim that their radio stations regularly launch educational campaigns on good governance in Nigeria. In other words, the radio stations in Delta State have various educational programmes that campaign for good governance in the nation. Data in the table also show that 100% of the respondents claim their radio station have programmes that enthrone the formation of democratic values and good governance in Nigeria.

In essence, the radio stations in Delta State have various that canvass for formation of democratic values among the leaders and the citizens for good governance in Nigeria. Results in the table also show

that over 86% of the respondents claim their radio station have programmes that tackle the government on the need to make and implement anti-corruption policies while about 13% of them said their radio stations do not have such programme. This implies that most of the radio stations in Delta State have various programmes that campaign for the implementation of anti-corruption policies by the government.

Data in the table also show that 90% of the respondents claim their radio station have programmes that boost citizens' participation in politics while 10% of them are not sure if their radio stations do not have such programme. This means that majority of the radio stations in Delta State have various programmes that educate and campaign for active participation of the populace in politics.

Results in the table also show that 90% of the respondents claim their radio station have programmes that mobilise citizens to demand for anti-corruption policy formulation and implementation in Nigeria while about 10% of them said their radio stations do not have such programme.

This implies that most of the radio stations in Delta State have various programmes that inform, educate and mobilize the masses citizens to demand for anti-corruption policy formulation and implementation from the government.

Finally, results in the table equally indicate that over 60% of the respondents claim their radio station have programmes that teach the citizens other specific actions to take against corrupt practices among government officials while about 35% of them said their radio stations do not have such programme. This means that some of the radio stations in Delta State do not have programmes that teach the masses other specific actions to take to make corrupt government officials make more accountable to the people.

RQ 4: Challenges that radio journalists in Delta State face in the promotion of good governance

The respondents identified the challenges that hinder effective promotion of good governance via their radio station as, accountability, transparency, lack of manpower, oppressive regulations, corruption, poor funding, out dated equipment, undue internal and external interference, noise and interferences from weather.

It is pertinent to note that all (100%) of the respondents identified lack of transparency and accountability as one of their challenges. In other words, those at the helm of affairs carry out shady deals or sharp practices that directly or indirectly undermine the use of radio to promote good governance in the State.

Literature reveals that observe that African journalists in Africa have a notorious reputation of "selling out" to proprietary, advertising and political controls (Skjerdal, 2010; White, 2010). The respondents equally suggested ways of resolving the challenges as, training and retraining of media practitioners, proper funding, regular and improved salary schemes for journalists and much more

Conclusion

The study concludes that a responsible media must perform services of informing, educating and entertaining the public in order to justify their existence. Nigeria's quest for good governance is achievable to the extent that the radio stations and other mass media can provide full, accurate and constructive coverage of the daily activities of the government.

Moreover, as societal watch dog, oxygen of democracy, radio journalists should realize that information is a social good and not a commodity. Thus, no matter the circumstances, journalists should maintain high standards of integrity when performing their social roles to the society. On this note the study recommended training and retraining of media practitioners and proper funding of broadcasting stations.

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